

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants (Table 2) with trivalent La, Pr, Ce, Nd, Sm, Gd and Dy were determined by Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique^{3,4}. The ligands **1a** and **1b** showed two buffer regions, one in acid medium (pH 4-5) and the other in basic medium (pH 6.5-8) corresponding to the release of protons of phenolic OH and azomethine ($-\overset{+}{C}=\text{NH}-$) groups, respectively. Ligands **1c** and **1d** showed only one buffer region (pH 7.5-8) corresponding to the release of phenolic proton which can be traced to the electron-withdrawing effect of Cl and NO₂ groups. The stability constants of lanthanide(III) complexes are almost in the increasing order of their Z^2/r values, suggesting that lanthanum(III)-ligand interaction to be primarily ionic. With respect to the ligands the stability order is **1b** > **1a** > Ahmc > **1c** > **1d** in accordance with relative basicities of ligands. Plots of $\log K_1$ ($\log \beta_1$) vs $\log K_{\text{OH}}^{\text{H}}$ of these ligands are linear for each metal-ligand system.

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The Influence of Thiourea on Gallium(III) Ion Reduction on DME

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IN most electrolytes, gallium(III) ions reduce on DME producing badly formed irreversible polarographic waves with maximum¹. The process is catalysed by thiocyanate and azide ions and also by an increase of the ionic strength of the solution^{2,3}. Some uni- and poly-valent anions and cations suppress the polarographic maximum and influence on the kinetics of electrode reaction of gallium(III)^{4,5}.

In our studies on the influence of surface active substances on Ga^{III} ions on DME we observed that the presence of thiourea (TU) in the solution affects the electrode process. Our aim in the present

study was to determine the changes in the kinetics and mechanism of Ga^{III} ion reduction on DME under the influence of TU. The investigation was carried out in two kinds of electrolytes: 6.0 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄ and 3.3 mol dm⁻³ NaSCN.

Experimental

The measurements were carried out in three-electrode system (DME, SCE, Hg pool) using dc and square wave polarography. In the latter method a Radelkis OH-104 polarograph was used. In order to obtain more accurate results of dc polarograph a system of a potentiostat, a linear sweep generator and a Aritma BAK 4T X-Y recorder was used. The rate of flow of the capillary was $m=2.61 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$; drop time $t=2.9 \text{ s}$ in 6.0 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄ solution with height of mercury column $h=1.085 \text{ m}$.

The Ga^{III} solutions were obtained from 4 N Ga(NO₃)₃ (International Enzymes Limited, England) by dissolving it in dilute HClO₄.

Gallium concentration was kept constant throughout the investigation at $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Thiourea, NaClO₄ and NaSCN solutions were prepared from analytically pure salts. The pH levels in NaClO₄ and NaSCN solutions were kept constant (2.1 and 3.3, respectively). At such pH levels the hydrogen wave did not interfere with Ga^{III} ion reduction and no gallium hydroxide precipitation took place⁶. The concentration of thiourea varied from 10^{-4} to $2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The measurements were carried out in an argon atmosphere at 25°. One series of measurements involved an addition of gelatine (0.002%). Water and mercury employed were distilled twice.

Results and Discussion

Influence of TU on Ga^{III} ion reduction in 6.0 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄ solution, pH=2.1: It follows from the results that the increasing TU concentration increases the limiting current of the electrode reaction of reduction of Ga^{III} ions on DME and as well the half-wave potential of the electrode process shifts towards positive potential. Various criteria for ascertaining the irreversibility of the polarographic reduction of Ga^{III} were applied⁶. These indicated the irreversible and diffusion nature of the reduction of Ga^{III} ions in 6.0 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄. Under such conditions gallium-thiourea complexes undergo reduction on DME and they are more electroactive than the aquo-Ga^{III} ions. The latter is suggested by the direction of half-wave potential shift. The maximum coordination number of the complexes calculated by the method of Lingane, is approximately $j=4$. Addition of gelatine to the solution produces no significant changes. This seems to point out to the formation of gallium-thiourea complexes inside the solution as blocking of the electrode surface by gelatine does not affect their formation.

The kinetic parameters αn_{α} and k_{th}^0 for the electrode reaction were calculated using the Koutecky method (Table 1). The diffusion coefficient $D_{Ga(III)} = 3.06 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ was used².

TABLE 1—VALUES OF KINETIC PARAMETERS OF Ga^{III} ION REDUCTION IN 6.0 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄ SOLUTION AT VARIABLE TU CONCENTRATION

C_{TU} mol dm ⁻³	$-E_{1/2}$ mV	i_{lim} μA	$E_{1/4} - E_{3/4}$	αn_{α}	k_{th}^0 cm s ⁻¹ × 10 ⁻³
0	1340	9.2	—	0.30	0.047
1 × 10 ⁻⁴	1320	9.5	0.155	0.33	0.18
1 × 10 ⁻³	1260	10.2	0.136	0.38	0.90
2 × 10 ⁻²	1234	10.0	0.123	0.42	4.40
1 × 10 ⁻²	1176	10.4	0.115	0.45	6.75
2 × 10 ⁻²	1140	10.9	0.123	0.42	9.45

The data reveal that the increase of the concentration of TU gives the increase of reversibility of the reduction reaction (increase of αn_{α}) as well as the acceleration of the electrode process (increase of k_{th}^0).

Influence of TU on Ga^{III} ion reduction in 3.3 mol dm⁻³ NaSCN solution, pH=3.3: Under these conditions one observes two reduction waves. In keeping with the observation of Mac Nevin and Moorhead⁷ the first wave is related to the reduction of gallium–thiocyanate complexes while the other is related to reduction of the products of Ga^{III} ion hydrolysis. Both a logarithmic analysis and the data from Tomeš criterion indicate that the first wave concerns a reversible process, and the other an irreversible one. Gallium–thiourea complexes also arise in the course of Ga^{III} ion reduction in NaSCN solutions at pH=3.3, where one observes a shift of second half-wave potentials towards positive potentials. This is evident both in dc and ac polarograms. Since the first wave is related to reduction of gallium–thiocyanate complexes and the second one to reduction of Ga^{III} ion hydrolysis products, one may conclude that TU eliminates water molecules from the coordination sphere and not thiocyanate ions. Such a conclusion is also supported by the fact that the presence of TU in the solution does not inhibit the catalytic influence of SCN⁻ ions on Ga^{III} ion reduction.

An increase of the pH of the solution probably causes displacement of SCN⁻ ions from gallium–thiocyanate complexes by OH⁻ ions. The increased current of Ga^{III} ion reduction suggests that the influence facilitates the catalytic action of TU on the process under consideration.

It follows from the data that the increase of reversibility and rate of the electrode process with increasing TU concentration in the solution is connected with the formation of gallium–thiourea complexes. As the catalytic action of most substances on electrode processes is related to ligand or active complex adsorption on the electrode surface⁸, it may well be said that in the present

study the forming complex underwent adsorption on mercury.

Ga^{III} ion reduction in the investigated electrolytes takes place in a potential range at which TU adsorbs on mercury via covalent bond between mercury and TU sulphur^{9,10}. On the other hand, TU coordinates metals via one S atom¹¹. Hence, the acceleration of the Ga^{III} ion reduction by TU may be due to the formation of Hg–S–Ga bridge which facilitates charge transfer. A similar mechanism was proposed¹² for the acceleration of Zn^{II} ions reduction on DME by thiourea.

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Conductance Behaviour of Calcium Salts of Fatty Acids in Non-aqueous Medium

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THE colloidal and other physicochemical properties of alkali and other metal soaps have already been extensively studied by several workers¹ but the alkaline earth metal soaps have not yet been thoroughly investigated. Recently, the conductance behaviour of the dilute solutions of calcium salts of higher fatty acids in non-aqueous solvents has been investigated^{2,3}. The present paper deals with the conductance behaviour of calcium caproate and valerate in chloroform and propylene glycol mixtures of varying compositions and the results have been used to calculate various parameters, viz. CMC, limiting molecular conductance, dissociation constant and nature of salts, in organic media.